

Freedom Beyond Escape: Oral Histories from the Underground Railroad Project

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Course Description:

This course examines the Underground Railroad not as a singular historical event, but as an ongoing, multigenerational practice of Black resistance, memory, and survival. Drawing on oral histories from the Underground Railroad Oral History Project, students will explore how descendants interpret, preserve, and live the legacy of freedom struggles. Through themes of land, memory, embodiment, faith, and kinship, the course reframes freedom as a lived, inherited, and evolving practice rather than a completed historical moment. Students will engage oral histories as archives, analyze historical figures and networks, and develop original research connecting past and present forms of Black resistance. Particular attention will be given to the ways descendants function as historians, genealogists, educators, and custodians of community memory. By centering descendant voices alongside historical narratives, the course highlights how freedom struggles are remembered, interpreted, and extended across generations.

Student Learning Objectives:

By the end of this course, students will be able to:

- Analyze oral history interviews as primary historical sources and evaluate their contributions to understanding Black history and memory.
- Examine the Underground Railroad as a networked system of resistance involving individuals, families, communities, and institutions.
- Compare descendant narratives with historical texts to identify continuities and differences in the ways freedom, resistance, and survival are remembered.
- Evaluate the roles of land, kinship, faith, memory, and embodiment in shaping Black experiences of freedom across generations.
- Interpret descendant oral histories using historical, cultural, and genealogical frameworks.
- Construct a research-based argument that integrates oral histories, historical narratives, and course readings.
- Develop a final project that demonstrates critical engagement with descendant narratives and the ongoing legacies of Black resistance.

Course Learning Outcomes:

By the end of the course, students will be able to:

- Analyze the Underground Railroad as a networked, collective system of resistance involving individuals, families, communities, and institutions.

- Analyze oral history interviews as primary historical sources and evaluate their contributions to understanding Black history, memory, and identity.
- Analyze how descendants interpret freedom as an ongoing, intergenerational practice through oral histories and historical narratives.
- Evaluate the roles of land, memory, faith, kinship, and embodiment in shaping Black experiences of resistance and survival.
- Interpret oral history narratives using historical, cultural, and genealogical frameworks.
- Develop a research-based or creative final project that engages descendant narratives and the ongoing legacies of Black freedom struggles.

Course Texts/Materials:

- URP Oral History Transcripts (primary sources- see full list below)
- Incidents in the Life of a Slave Girl by Harriet Ann Jacobs
- Behind the Scenes, Or, Thirty Years a Slave and Four Years in the White House by Elizabeth Hobbs Keckley
- Reckoning with Slavery: Gender, Kinship and Capitalism by Jennifer Morgan
- The Narrative of Sojourner Truth by Sojourner Truth
- The Life of Josiah Henson, Formerly a Slave by Josiah Henson

Suggested Format:

- 2x weekly 90-minute discussion sessions
- Participation: Students must come prepared to discuss assigned transcripts and readings.

Assignments:

Weekly Reflection Journals- 20%

- Each week, students will submit a short reflection (approximately 1–2 pages) engaging with the assigned readings and oral history transcripts. These reflections should move beyond summary to offer critical analysis, drawing connections between descendant narratives and key course themes such as memory, land, kinship, embodiment, and resistance. Students are encouraged to reference specific moments from the transcripts and place them in conversation with course texts. These reflections are intended to help students prepare for discussion, develop their analytical voice, and begin identifying themes that may inform their midterm and final projects.

Oral History Analysis- 20%

- For this assignment, students will conduct a close reading of a single URP oral history transcript, treating it as a primary historical source and a form of knowledge production.

Students should analyze the interview for its narrative structure, key themes, silences, and the ways memory is constructed and conveyed. Attention should also be given to the role of the interviewer, the context of the interview, and how the descendant situates their family history within broader historical frameworks. This assignment emphasizes methodological awareness, encouraging students to think critically about oral history as both archive and interpretation.

Midterm Paper- 30% (5–7 pages)

- The midterm paper asks students to develop a focused analytical essay examining one major course theme: memory, land, networks, or embodiment. Using at least two URP oral history transcripts and one or more course readings, students will construct an argument about how that theme operates across descendant narratives. Papers should demonstrate close reading, engagement with course concepts, and an ability to connect individual stories to broader historical and theoretical frameworks. This assignment is designed to help students synthesize course material at the midpoint of the semester and begin practicing sustained analytical writing.

Final Project- 30% (Choose One)

- For the final project, students will choose one of four options that allows them to engage course themes in a substantive and creative way. Students may write a traditional research paper (10–15 pages) that draws on multiple transcripts and course readings to advance a clear argument about freedom, memory, or resistance. Alternatively, students may conduct their own oral history interview and submit both the interview and a reflective analysis. Students may also create a digital archive exhibit that curates and interprets selected descendant narratives, or design a curriculum or teaching module that translates course materials for a specific audience (K–12, community education, etc.). Regardless of format, all projects should demonstrate critical engagement with course concepts and a thoughtful approach to representing Black historical memory.

Component	Percentage
Participation & Discussion	10%
Weekly Reflections	15%
Oral History Analysis	20%
Midterm Paper	25%
Final Project	30%

Assignment Rubrics:

Participation Rubric (10%)

Criteria	Excellent (A)	Proficient (B)	Developing (C)	Unsatisfactory (D/F)
Preparation	Consistently completes readings and demonstrates deep familiarity with materials	Usually prepared and references readings	Limited preparation	Rarely prepared
Engagement	Regularly contributes thoughtful comments and questions	Participates consistently	Participates occasionally	Rarely participates
Respectful Dialogue	Actively listens and respectfully engages others	Generally respectful and collaborative	Occasionally disengaged	Disruptive or disrespectful
Evidence-Based Discussion	Uses readings and transcripts to support ideas	Frequently references course materials	Limited use of evidence	Rarely references course materials

Weekly Reflection Journals (20%)

Criteria	Excellent (A)	Proficient (B)	Developing (C)	Beginning (D/F)
Engagement with Readings & Transcripts (30%)	Demonstrates deep engagement with readings and transcripts; integrates specific examples	Demonstrates clear engagement with course materials	References readings but with limited depth	Minimal engagement with assigned materials
Critical Analysis (30%)	Moves beyond summary and offers thoughtful analysis of themes and connections	Includes some analysis with limited complexity	Primarily descriptive with little analysis	Mostly summary or unsupported opinions
Connection to Course Themes (20%)	Clearly connects ideas to course concepts (memory, land, kinship, resistance, embodiment, etc.)	Makes connections to course themes	Limited connection to course themes	No meaningful connection to course themes
Writing Quality (20%)	Well-organized, clear, and free of major errors	Generally clear with minor errors	Organization or clarity issues present	Significant writing issues impede understanding

Oral History Analysis (20%)

Criteria	Excellent (A)	Proficient (B)	Developing (C)	Beginning (D/F)
Analysis of Transcript (30%)	Demonstrates sophisticated analysis of oral history narrative	Demonstrates clear analysis	Limited analysis	Minimal analysis
Use of Evidence (25%)	Effectively incorporates specific examples from transcript	Uses examples appropriately	Limited use of examples	Little or no textual evidence
Methodological Awareness (25%)	Insightfully addresses oral history as archive and method	Addresses methodological issues clearly	Limited discussion of methodology	Little awareness of methodology
Writing & Organization (20%)	Well-structured and polished	Generally organized and clear	Some organizational issues	Difficult to follow

Midterm Paper (30%)

Criteria	Excellent (A)	Proficient (B)	Developing (C)	Beginning (D/F)
Argument & Thesis (25%)	Clear, original, and compelling argument	Clear argument	Basic or underdeveloped argument	No clear argument
Use of Course Materials (25%)	Integrates transcripts and readings effectively	Uses required sources appropriately	Limited integration of sources	Insufficient use of sources
Analysis of Theme (25%)	Demonstrates nuanced understanding of selected theme	Demonstrates understanding of theme	Limited exploration of theme	Minimal engagement with theme
Organization & Writing (25%)	Well-organized and polished	Mostly organized and clear	Some writing or organizational issues	Significant issues

Final Project Rubric Option A: Research Paper (10–15 pages)

Criteria:

- Argument & Thesis (25%)
- Use of Transcripts and Course Readings (25%)
- Critical Analysis (25%)
- Writing, Organization, and Citation (25%)

Final Project Rubric Option B: Oral History Project

Criteria:

- Interview Preparation and Question Design (20%)
- Quality of Interview Documentation (20%)
- Reflective Analysis (30%)
- Connection to Course Themes (30%)

Final Project Rubric Option C: Digital Archive Exhibit

Criteria:

- Selection and Interpretation of Materials (25%)
- Historical Accuracy (25%)
- Organization and Accessibility (25%)
- Analytical Commentary and Contextualization (25%)

Final Project Rubric Option D: Curriculum or Teaching Module

Criteria:

- Alignment with Learning Objectives (25%)
- Historical Accuracy and Use of Sources (25%)
- Pedagogical Design and Engagement (25%)
- Reflection and Rationale (25%)

Course Policies

Attendance and Participation

Because this course is discussion-based and centers collaborative learning through oral histories, regular attendance and participation are expected. Students should arrive prepared to discuss assigned readings and transcripts and contribute thoughtfully to class discussions. More than two unexcused absences may negatively affect a student's participation grade. Students with excused absences, consistent with university policy, will be provided opportunities to make up missed work. Participation includes attendance, engagement in discussion, preparation of readings, and respectful interaction with peers.

Communication Policy

Students should allow 24–48 hours for email responses during the work week. Emails received on weekends or university holidays will be answered during the next business day. Students are encouraged to communicate proactively regarding questions, assignment concerns, or unexpected circumstances that may affect course participation.

Technology and Submission Policy

Assignments should be submitted through Canvas by the designated deadline. Students experiencing technical difficulties should contact the university help desk immediately and retain documentation of the issue. Requests for extensions due to technical difficulties must be accompanied by appropriate documentation and communicated to the instructor as soon as possible.

Classroom Netiquette Policy

This course relies on thoughtful discussion and engagement with sensitive topics including slavery, racism, freedom, identity, religion, and memory. Students are expected to:

- Engage respectfully with classmates and interview participants.
- Listen actively and respond thoughtfully to differing viewpoints.
- Critique ideas rather than individuals.
- Support claims with evidence from readings and course materials.
- Maintain a classroom environment that values intellectual curiosity, empathy, and mutual respect.

Disrespectful behavior, personal attacks, harassment, or discriminatory language will not be tolerated.

Use of Oral Histories

The oral histories used in this course represent personal memories, family histories, and lived experiences. Students should approach these materials with care, recognizing descendants as knowledge holders, historical interpreters, and community historians.

Students may not reproduce, distribute, or publicly share transcripts or interview materials outside the course without permission.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Policy

The purpose of this course is to strengthen students' abilities to analyze historical sources, interpret oral histories, and develop original arguments. Because these skills require independent critical thinking, all submitted work must represent the student's own intellectual labor.

Students may use AI tools for limited support activities such as brainstorming, outlining, or proofreading. However, AI-generated writing may not be submitted as original work. Any use of AI must be acknowledged in a brief statement attached to the assignment describing how the tool was used.

Students remain fully responsible for the accuracy, originality, and integrity of all submitted work. Failure to disclose substantial AI use may be treated as a violation of academic integrity policies.

Unit I: Rethinking the Underground Railroad (Weeks 1–3)

Week	Topic	Readings	Discussion	Assignment	Descendant Connection
1	What Was the Underground Railroad?	URP Oral History Transcripts (intro selections)	Why is the Underground Railroad misunderstood? What changes when we center networks?	Reflection #1	N/A
2	The Underground Railroad as a Network	<i>The Life of Josiah Henson</i> (selections); URP transcripts	How did collaboration function? Why were networks necessary? How does Robert Seeley's interpretation of Thomas Garrett expand our understanding of Underground Railroad networks?	Discussion post	Robert Seeley → Thomas Garrett
3	Law, Violence, and Risk	<i>The Life of Josiah Henson</i> (continued); URP Transcript: Ocea Bolden Thomas	What risks did conductors face? How do Ocea Thomas's efforts to secure a posthumous pardon for Samuel D. Burris illustrate the ongoing consequences of historical injustice?	Discussion Post	Ocea Bolden Thomas → Samuel D. Burris

Unit II: Networks, Risk, Resistance (Weeks 4–6)

Week	Topic	Readings	Discussion	Assignment	Descendant Connection
4	Black Agency and Resistance	<p><i>The Narrative of Sojourner Truth</i></p> <p>URP Transcript: Regina Mason</p>	<p>Why are some Black freedom narratives remembered while others are overlooked?</p> <p>How does Regina Mason's recovery of William Grimes's story challenge traditional narratives of slavery and freedom?</p>	Reflection #2	Regina Mason → William Grimes
5	Women, Family, and Hidden Labor	<p><i>Incidents in the Life of a Slave Girl; Behind the Scenes</i>; URP Transcript: Margaret "Peggy" Trotter Dammond Preacely</p>	<p>How did Black women navigate systems of power, gender, and racial oppression?</p> <p>How does the story of Ellen Craft complicate ideas about race, gender, and freedom?</p>	Discussion post	Peggy Trotter Dammond Preacely → Ellen and William Craft

6	Trust, Secrecy, and Community	URP transcripts (network + community focus)	How did trust function as infrastructure? What made networks possible?	Midterm Reflection Due	Multiple URP descendants
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Unit III: Memory, Land, Embodiment (Weeks 7–10)

Week	Topic	Readings	Discussion	Assignment	Descendant Connection
7	Oral History as Method	URP transcripts (method-focused selection)	What counts as an archive? How do we read oral histories critically?	Oral history analysis	All interviewees
8	Memory as Practice	URP transcripts (Louise Miller Cohen, Wilton Russell, Sharona Woodside-Barr)	<p>What does it mean to "live" memory?</p> <p>How do descendants become custodians of family and community histories?</p> <p>How do memory practices differ across Gullah Geechee and Black Seminole traditions?</p>	Reflection #3	<p>Louise Miller Cohen → Cesar Jones</p> <p>Wilton Russell → Black Seminole descendants (Red Bays, Bahamas)</p>

					Sharona Woodside-Barr → Black Seminole descendants
9	Land, Property, and Inheritance	<i>Reckoning with Slavery</i> (Jennifer Morgan); URP transcripts (Louise Miller Cohen, Marsha Mills Ortiz, Arthur Thomas)	<p>How does land function as freedom?</p> <p>What is inherited across generations?</p> <p>What happens when communities lose land?</p> <p>How do settlements become archives of Black life?</p>	Discussion Post	<p>Louise Miller Cohen → Cesar Jones / Gullah Geechee land stewardship</p> <p>Marsha Mills Ortiz → Gist Settlement</p> <p>Arthur Thomas → Rumley Settlement</p>
10	Embodiment and Movement	URP transcripts (Anthony Cohen, Tina Dunkley, Ajena Rogers)	<p>How does the body carry history?</p> <p>What does it mean to retrace ancestral journeys?</p> <p>How do movement, migration, and place shape identity?</p>	Discussion Post	<p>Anthony Cohen → Patrick Sneed</p> <p>Tina Dunkley → Ezekiel Loney</p> <p>Ajena Rogers → Hanover County /</p>

			How do descendants physically engage the past?		Black Appalachian lineage
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Unit IV: Descendants & Living Legacies (Weeks 11–14)

Week	Topic	Readings	Discussion	Assignment	Descendant Connection
11	Genealogy and Discovery	URP transcripts (Ocea Thomas focus)	How is history discovered? What is the role of genealogy?	Research proposal for final project	Ocea Bolden Thomas → Samuel D. Burris
12	Descendants as Historians	URP transcripts (Robert Seeley, Regina Mason, Bruce Purnell, Carl J. Cruz)	Who has authority to tell history? How do descendants become historians, genealogists, educators, and public memory keepers?	Discussion	Robert Seeley, Regina Mason, Bruce Purnell, Carl J. Cruz
13	Public Memory and Recognition	URP transcripts (Burris pardon, Grimes, public history cases)	What does it mean to remember publicly? Who gets recognized?	Draft final project	Ocea Thomas; Regina Mason

14	Freedom as Ongoing Practice	URP transcripts (course-wide synthesis)	Is freedom complete? What does liberation look like today?	Final Project Due	
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URP Interviewees and Historical Connections

The Underground Railroad Oral History Project includes descendants connected to historical figures, family lineages, free Black settlements, Black Seminole communities, and other collective histories. The chart below provides an overview of the ancestral and historical connections represented in the interviews used throughout this course.

Interviewee(s)	Ancestor(s) Named
Robert E. Seeley	Thomas Garrett
Ocea Bolden Thomas	Samuel D. Burris
Regina Mason	William Grimes
Margaret “Peggy” Trotter Dammond Preacely	Ellen Craft, William Craft
William Gould IV	William B. Gould
Kimberly L. Simmons	William B. Gould (referenced lineage)
Anthony Cohen	Patrick Sneed
Tina Dunkley	Ezekiel Loney
Louise Cohen	Cesar Jones

Bruce Purnell	Family connections to Martin Delany, Mary Ann Shadd Cary, and John Brown networks
Wilton Russell	Black Seminoles (Red Bays, Bahamas)
Sharona Woodside-Barr	Black Seminoles / Bahamian lineage
Peggy-Ann Colebrooke, Kendrick Wallace	Black Seminole descendants
Thomas Mitchell & Bossie H. Hawkins	Negro Fort survivors, Black Seminoles
LaKeesha Morrison, Don Drife, Bob Muller	Black pioneers (Canada → Michigan)
Marsha Mills Ortiz	Gist Settlement (Ohio)
Arthur Thomas	Rumley, Ohio settlement
Reita Ann Smith & Mark Evans	Underground Railroad families; Black-Indigenous (Shawnee)
Peggy Mills Warner	Free Black settlement lineage
James Settles	Black church/community lineage
Derrick Still Mayes	Family lineage (not tied to named figure)

Michael Moore	Migration-based family lineage
Courtney Scott	Black education/community lineage
Ajena Rogers	Hanover County / Black Appalachian lineage
Eric Sheppard & Chris Lowie	Migration + regional memory
Janet Lamborn & Taylor Lamborn	Family memory transmission
Darlene Colón	Afro-Caribbean lineage
Stephanie Gilbert	Black education/community lineage
Jason A. Brown Sr.	Migration lineage
Daphney Towns	Gendered family memory lineage
Carl J. Cruz	William H. Carney (54th Massachusetts Regiment)